

INNOVATIVE BLOCKCHAIN TRACEABILITY TECHNOLOGY AND STAKEHOLDERS' ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY FOR BOOSTING SUSTAINABLE SEAFOOD VISIBILITY, SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE AND CONSUMPTION IN EUROPE

D7.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan

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DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
DMP	Data management plan	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ethics	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	<input type="checkbox"/>
SECURITY	Deliverables related to security issues	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Current seafood traceability tools and services have the potential to take advantage of novel blockchain technologies to obtain a wide range of data making sustainable seafood practices more visible to consumers. SEA2SEE project will fill in existing seafood traceability gaps through development and demonstration of an innovative end-to-end blockchain traceability model throughout the seafood value chain and professional and consumer applications to increase trust and social acceptance of sustainably fished and farmed seafood.

The project will provide technological solutions to answer the need for a valuable source of data collected throughout the whole seafood value chain, verified and covering inputs from diverse stakeholders. For that purpose, a specific focus will be put on active commitment of stakeholders and real empowerment of consumers through the implementation of societal and sectoral strategies for co-creation, communication and awareness raising.

The project runs from July 2022 to June 2026. It involves 14 partners from 6 EU countries and is coordinated by SMARTWATER PLANET S.L., Spain.

More information about the project can be found at: <http://www.sea2see.eu/>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Plan for Dissemination and Communication (D7.2) is a strategic document outlining SEA2SEE Consortium's goals and vision for the communication and dissemination of the project, the associated activities in their support, target audience, communication channels and key messages. It is a primary reference tool, which includes the methods, approaches and communication campaigns that will be deployed to effectively build broad awareness about the project, raise its visibility, amplify the impact of its outcomes and their uptake by the industry, and eventually, empower a large number of end-users' acceptance of the SEA2SEE digital solutions, thus contributing to a more sustainable, environmentally friendly, inclusive, safe and healthy seafood consumption in Europe. The Plan supports all main objectives of the Communication, Dissemination and Outreach work package (WP7), namely:

- maximize project's visibility
- support engagement of stakeholder groups in a continuous dialogue
- raise awareness of the project and its topics among the wider public
- promote the activities, tools and outcomes of the project

The Communication and Dissemination Plan is a living document that is subject to updates throughout the duration of the project in case there is a necessity to adapt it to the project progress. The main purpose of this document is to serve as a competent and relevant means of reference as far as the communication and dissemination activities are concerned but also to provide a mechanism for evaluating their impact, during and after the lifespan of SEA2SEE.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan is an integral part of the whole communication deliverables package, that is the Synergy Plan (D7.4), Project website and social media (D7.1), Report on the Dissemination and Communication activities (D7.3) and the communication toolbox.

ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
CD	Communication and Dissemination
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
DG ENV	Directorate-General for Environment
DG MARE	Directorate General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
DG RTD	Directorate General for Research & Innovation
DGPM	EU Directorate General of Maritime Policy
DGRM	Directorate General for Natural Resources Safety and Maritime Services
DMP	Data Management Plan
EAPO	European Association of Fish Producers Organizations
EC	European Commission
EMD	Eropean Maritime Day
ETIP	European Technology and Innovation Platform
EU EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
FAO	UN Food and Agriculture Organization
FEAP	Federation of European Aquaculture Producers
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MOOC	Massive Open Online Courses
NGO	Non-governmental Organization
REA	Research and Executive Agency
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation

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1. INTRODUCTION

SEA2SEE is a technologically challenging project. The understanding and acceptance of its ambitious goals and complex results by a largely diverse group of stakeholders from the whole seafood value chain, appears to be demanding and calls for an effective and well-coordinated communication and dissemination effort. A strategic Communication and Dissemination (CD) Plan, with clearly defined communication goals, target groups, and messages, channels and tools tailored to the respective audience groups is instrumental for the project's success. Ultimately, it will nurture interest and significant increase in the implementation of innovative digital and data sharing tools, supporting the achievement of full sustainable seafood traceability.

The current CD Plan comprises all the necessary components required to ensure productive promotion of the project and distribution of its outcomes. It is linked to **task T7.1** which is effective during, and after the end of project. The plan is composed with the participation of all members of the Consortium while relying mostly on the contributions of WP1 and WP2 partners to ensure consistency with the strategies they are developing for effective stakeholders' engagement, from industry to end-consumers. It is made available to all project partners and on the project website too. Updates or adjustments of the proposed herein activities are considered, with the evolution of the project's implementation and whether the set objectives are being reached. A final report on the conducted communication and dissemination activities, and their impact, is envisaged to be delivered at the end of the project.

1.1. SCOPE

Dissemination and communication activities are considered of utmost importance for the successful achievement of the SEA2SEE project objectives. According to the definitions proposed by the Horizon Europe Programme Guide¹, recently published by the EC, communication on projects “starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results”, while dissemination pertains to “the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium”. These definitions clearly distinguish between the main purpose of each of the above activities, with the former being predominantly informative, addressing multiple audiences, to include media and broad public, while the latter is focusing on transferring knowledge and results, enabling their utilization by interested stakeholders such as industry partners, academia or policy makers, thus maximizing the impact of the EU research.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan of SEA2SEE adopts the above understanding in the development of a strategy considering both online and offline communication tools. It aims to reach and engage diverse user personas from the entire spectrum of the seafood value chain, and includes targeted

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

messaging and positioning statements to ensure wide impact at various levels of knowledge and areas of implementation. Last but not least, it encompasses communication and dissemination campaigns with adapted means and language so that the identified stakeholder audiences (from consumers, to include vulnerable groups, to academics, producers, private sector and media) are successfully reached. This does not only provide for project's increased visibility but also highlights its approach to technology design that is tailored to stakeholders' local, regional, national and international needs, which is recognized as beneficial.

1.2. VISION AND OBJECTIVES

SEA2SEE ambition is to significantly elevate consumer trust and acceptance of sustainably fished or farmed seafood in Europe through the development and demonstration of an innovative end-to-end blockchain based traceability platform throughout the seafood value chain. Furthermore, it aspires to implement societal and sectoral strategies for co-creation, communication and awareness raising about the advantages of sustainable and nutritious seafood fishing and aquaculture. In order to trigger a transition towards more sustainable options for seafood consumption across European consumers, the vision of SEA2SEE CD Plan is to spread knowledge and information about its activities in a coherent, strategic and impactful way, led by the following general objectives:

- To inform and raise awareness about the project and its research outputs through communication tools and campaigns;
- To engage with relevant stakeholders, from civil society to policy makers to strategically selected target groups, to foster wide acceptance and adoption of project's methodology and results;
- To promote the alignment of technology innovation with environmental and food safety policies, and existing certification practices and labels;
- To distribute technology research and development findings to various audiences within the academic community through peer reviewed publications, conferences and seminars;
- To cluster and create synergies with relevant EU and national projects on seafood traceability, and production process accountability and digitization for knowledge transfer and capacity building;
- To ensure exploitation of project results and follow-up on potential regulatory and business opportunities through policies and implementation.

The above objectives along with the main goal of the CD Plan - to ensure large-scale acceptance of project's results and maximize its socio-economic impact through the active involvement of cross-sectoral groups of stakeholders - will be achieved with the means of various communication and dissemination campaigns, engaging consumers through participatory strategies demonstrating how web-based and digital tools can provide trustworthy traceability information. Additionally, the dissemination strategy of the project is built in compliance with the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) concept and the Open Science policy based on open cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge and tools as early and widely as possible.

2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

The Communication and Dissemination Plan should not be considered simply a visibility booster but an empowerment tool rather, for a larger number of end-users to uptake the SEA2SEE digital solutions. Consequently, embracing innovative information strategies and technology platforms leads to a more sustainable, environmentally friendly, inclusive, safe and healthy seafood consumption.

Communication activities involve the integrated use of mass media and digital distribution channels to share relevant information, raise awareness and educate about the possibilities the project brings for engaging a multitude of value chain stakeholders in a co-creation process and continuous dialogue for increased responsibility and potential public behavior change towards more sustainable seafood fishery, and aquaculture practices in Europe. Ultimately, actors applying such practices become more visible to consumers, thus giving them a competitive advantage.

The maintenance of a consistent image, messaging tailored to the specific audiences, translating the meaning of complex technological terms to the level of comprehension of each target category lay the foundation for the broadest possible outreach of the project and opens opportunities for direct stakeholders' involvement as well as cross-communication and dissemination.

Beneficiary institutions and individuals involved in SEA2SEE act as ambassadors for the project and interpreters of its results. From its very beginning, the project starts promoting its goals and objectives, framework, preliminary results and any project achievements, with suitably framed messages delivered through a proper medium.

The CD plan of SEA2SEE constitutes the reference document for all dissemination and communication implementation and is developed to respond to the following strategic questions:

- Who are we talking to – target groups of stakeholders;
- What do we want to say – the messages SEA2SEE partners would like to bring across;
- Why are we doing it – the impact SEA2SEE wants to achieve;
- How do we do it – the relevant activities, tools and channels that are to be employed to reach the communicative goals, accompanied by guidelines and templates for Consortium partners to disseminate and communicate project results;
- When do we do it – the timing and frequency of CD activities in order for them to be most effective.

The following table (Table 1) proposes a summarized view of the Communication and Dissemination Plan, which is flexible in nature, pulling together the work and information from different work packages and stakeholders' meetings, conducted by project partners during the project and following its end. Further level of granularity regarding communication activities planning for stakeholders' engagement in WP1 and WP2, in particular, is expected to be found in their respective deliverables.

Who	What/Why	How	
		<i>During the project</i>	<i>After the project, Legacy</i>
<p>Consumers and the general public (end-consumers, consumer associations, EU/national NGOs dealing with sustainability)</p>	<p>Inform and engage the public, increase social acceptance of sustainable seafood;</p> <p>Sustainability in the seafood industry – what does it mean in practical terms;</p> <p>Rights and responsibilities of consumers when choosing seafood;</p> <p>Breaking misconceptions regarding aquaculture and fishing;</p> <p>Social reception of needed technological solutions leads to long-lasting impact for citizen wellbeing.</p>	<p>Social media content easily accessible and understandable; Newsletter, 3 popular science articles in national or local media; 3 press releases; social media curious facts campaign, most popular seafood in your country, international and little-known seafood recipes; offline public engagement campaign through media and on-site events.</p> <p>Examples: Book of recipes, MOOC, Roadmap of your catch video).</p>	<p>Project website, social media, project video, online promotional material.</p>
<p>Seafood value chain actors (producers, suppliers, processors, retailers, professional associations)</p>	<p>Inform about and co-create SEA2SEE innovative solution for blockchain based traceability platform for fisheries and aquaculture alike;</p> <p>Raise their awareness on the project, expected outcomes and wider impacts;</p> <p>Direct contact and involvement of large supermarket chains;</p> <p>Aquaculture and fisheries stakeholders engaged through European and national sector associations (FEAP, EAPO) and the European Aquaculture Society.</p>	<p>Partners network of contacts; WP1 participatory process; WP2 visits to harbors; WP5 demo activities;</p> <p>6 project presentations, Stakeholder workshop with brokerage events, Capacity building workshops, SEA2SEE final conferences, External events participation (i.e. congresses, trade shows), Social media, Website, Project video.</p>	<p>Social Media, Project website, Project video, Joint proposal applications.</p>

<p>Investors and other interested business</p>	<p>Inform about and demonstrate SEA2SEE solution and how it could be scaled, reused and replicated for increasing trust, traceability and responsible consumption of sustainable seafood.</p>	<p>6 project presentations, Stakeholder brokerage events, demonstrations, SEA2SEE final conference, External events participation (i.e., congresses, trade shows, symposiums), social media, Website, Project video.</p>	<p>Social media, Project website, project video, press release, Joint proposal applications.</p>
<p>Scientific community</p>	<p>The applied research and innovation approaches and results improve the research background of digital traceability and transparency of seafood;</p> <p>Be informed about and feed information into the project;</p> <p>Knowledge exchange.</p>	<p>Scientific Journals (4 peer review publications), synergies building activities, stakeholder meetings, conferences, symposia, workshops; newsletter, website.</p>	<p>Joint proposal applications, Project website; Networking</p>
<p>Public authorities and policy makers</p>	<p>Inform about project’s objectives and digital technological solution contributing to safer and healthier seafood consumption through improved transparency, and therefore credibility;</p> <p>Represent SEA2SEE interests and outputs to decision makers, bridge societal - policy gap;</p> <p>Ensuring compliance and alignment to socio-economic needs;</p> <p>Recommendations on actions regarding food security and EU-mandated traceability systems to encourage transparency and accountability in seafood supply.</p>	<p>Final conference workshop with brokerage events;</p> <p>Social media campaigns targeting local and national stakeholders;</p> <p>Website, newsletter, project videos, articles, webinars, conferences, seminars; Dedicated publications, presentations at seminars and international events including policy makers, SEA2SEE final conference.</p>	<p>Project website, Project video.</p>
<p>Related EU research projects and initiatives</p>	<p>Ensure synergies, existing or to be established, to enhance acceptability and visibility of SEA2SEE outcomes and foster their uptake by respective value chain actors;</p>	<p>Synergies building with 4 relevant projects and clustering activities, articles, SEA2SEE final conference, ETIP event participation, joint participation in events.</p>	<p>Clustering initiatives, Joint proposal applications, Project website.</p>

	Best practices and experience exchange for increasing project's impact.		
Horizon Europe Missions	<p>Establish contact and collaborate with Horizon Europe Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change for societal transformation and climate resilient planet;</p> <p>Co-creation and co-participatory events engaging end consumers in climate adaptation policy development.</p>	<p>Networking, press release, newsletter, website;</p> <p>Workshops, seminars, joint events with sister projects, workshop at EMD;</p> <p>Presentations at conferences, trade shows, exhibitions.</p>	<p>Project website;</p> <p>Joint proposal applications.</p>

Table 1. Dissemination and Communication Strategy - a snapshot

2.1. TARGET AUDIENCE

In the framework of the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) concept and the Open Science policy, societal actors of various walks of life, such as researchers, citizens, public authorities, non-governmental organizations, professional associations, businesses, work together during the research and innovation process to align its outcomes with the needs, values and expectations of society, which could be represented through the Quadruple Helix Innovation Model below.

Figure 1. Quadruple Helix Innovation Model

This approach has been utilized to define the target audience within SEA2SEE and several stakeholder profiles have been identified:

2.1.1. CONSUMERS AND GENERAL PUBLIC

Consumers typically represent the end users of the seafood value chain. They are members of the society who do not fit any of the other three helixes of the interaction and form the basis of a bottom-up social innovation and therefore seem to constitute one of the most important target groups for SEA2SEE. Consumers in this sense are the end-users, consumer associations, EU/national NGOs dealing with food sustainability as factor for security and stability, and others.

Keeping the public at large well informed and engaged with the project and its deliverables, from the early stages of the activities, is considered crucial for building positive public perception and subsequent social acceptance of needed technological solutions for sustainable seafood with low environmental and carbon footprint, which in turn leads to longer-lasting impact for the citizens' wellbeing, especially in the EU framework of resilient societies and reaching climate neutrality.

The full spectrum of one-way communication channels and tools is utilized: promotional materials, press releases, newsletter, project's website and two videos introducing the project in a visually appealing and easily understandable language. All these channels are aided by the employed interactivity of the four social media accounts of SEA2SEE. To disperse the lack of consumer trust in the transparency of the EU seafood products, communication action needs to also focus on raising consumers' Ocean literacy and provide them with personalized information and tools, motivating a behavioral change towards informed decisions, paving the way to their becoming an active part of the end-to-end seafood value chain.

2.1.2. SEAFOOD VALUE CHAIN ACTORS AND BUSINESS

Perhaps the largest, this group comprises the professionals, from producers and suppliers to processors and retailers of different scale. SEA2SEE communication and dissemination looks to encompass all type of seafood supply chain stakeholders such as fishermen and fish farmers, auction managers, fisheries authorities, major buyers and transformation industry, fishmongers and chefs. Important units such as large supermarket chains of outstanding seafood producers are reached through direct contacts based on the networks of SEA2SEE partners contracts. Additionally, aquaculture and fishery stakeholders are largely engaged though European and national sector associations such as the Federation of European Aquaculture Producers (FEAP), European Association of Fish Producers Organizations (EAPO), as well as the European Aquaculture Society. Another possible avenue of approach is the EU 'Taste the Ocean' campaign involving celebrity chefs from all over Europe to encourage consumers to buy and enjoy sustainable fish and seafood.

In addition to all partners being responsible for the communication and dissemination effort, the direct participation of WP1, WP2, WP5 and WP6 enhances strongly the SEA2SEE messages to all type of actors across the value chain through their respective activities: participatory process, visits to harbours,

demonstration activities and lifecycle, hazardous and benefits analysis associated to seafood consumption.

Seafood value chain stakeholders are the bodies that intend to implement the novel technology, test and validate it in the respective demo work packages, which requires robust exploitation plans, risk and benefit assessments, and methodologies. They will also benefit from the networking opportunities in the project. Focused dissemination and exploitation activities are of paramount importance for this group.

Clearly, the scaling and wide adoption of a novel, still unpopular digital solution for better transparency and traceability of sustainable seafood requires significant financial support. Therefore, starting from the second third of the project's duration, targeted communication effort towards public and private investors, banks or venture funds are to be intensified in terms of promoting and demonstrating SEA2SEE solution and ensuring it is operationalized in a growing number of value chain actors.

2.1.3. SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY AND ACADEMIA

This group is meant to include the academia and research community in the field of food security, in general, and seafood traceability and sustainability, in particular. Some EU initiatives could also be ascribed to here.

Suitable niche for disseminating SEA2SEE results is the powered by the EU EIT Food community (European Institute of Innovation and Technology) - a European network accelerating innovation to build a future-fit food system that produces healthy and sustainable food for all.

The SEA2SEE Research and Innovation approaches and results improve the research background of digital traceability and transparency of seafood. Project's progress, activities and technological developments are regularly communicated to the above preliminary noted scientific communities and platforms so as to influence subsequent usage of the outcomes. The engagement with them allows for quality dissemination of news related to the advantages of digitizing seafood sustainability activities, and their applications, towards the broader public and a multitude of diverse stakeholders.

2.1.4. PUBLIC AUTHORITIES AND POLICY MAKERS

In the context of SEA2SEE, public actors refer to governmental bodies within nutrition, environmental management, maritime policy, regional development, which formulate, adopt, implement, evaluate, or change environmental and nutrition-related policies. These might include institutions dedicated to the governance of food traceability and sustainable practices, the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), but also institutions with broader focus on Ocean conservation, citizens' social wellbeing, circular economy, climate change and biodiversity as well as local organizations. Some examples are the Research and Executive

Agency (REA) of the EC, the funding authority for SEA2SEE, DG Health and Consumers, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (DG RTD), Directorate-General for Environment (DG ENV), UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), EU Directorate General of Maritime Policy (DGPM), Directorate General for Natural Resources Safety and Maritime Services (DGRM),) Directorate General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE), national legislators, national ministries, as well as regional and local authorities in SEA2SEE partners' countries, such as DocaPesca for example - the public company which manages all fishing port areas and fish landings in Portugal.

2.1.5. OTHER RESEARCH PROJECTS, INITIATIVES AND HORIZON EUROPE MISSIONS

Linking SEA2SEE with related EU projects and initiatives in the realm of sustainability and delivering solutions for a transparent and traceable seafood supply chain enhances the acceptability and visibility of the project's outcomes and fosters their uptake by the industry. At the same time, being connected with similar projects highlights opportunities for collaboration, inter-linkages and the possibility of feeding into, and transferring SEA2SEE results to other projects and knowledge areas (cf. D7.4 Synergy Plan).

Collaborating with the boards of Horizon Europe Missions is charged with significant potential for boosting SEA2SEE visibility but also to practically contribute to a more resilient, greener, healthier and inclusive society through the technological seafood traceability solution it develops. EU Missions are a novelty of the Horizon Europe research and innovation program and they aim to bring tangible benefits to people in Europe and engage Europeans in their design, implementation and monitoring. SEA2SEE targets three of the five missions, namely: Adaptation to Climate Change, Restore our Ocean and Waters, and 100 Climate Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030.

2.2. KEY MESSAGES

Key messages are developed to ensure a uniform and consistent voice of the project while communicating its key goals, objectives and impacts. They are defined with partners' contributions, distributed to them and embedded in all communication and dissemination actions related to the project. Each key message communicates a specific idea and therefore resonates best with the specific target audience and context it is designed for. Along the project timeline, and circumstance dependent, the messages can change or be adapted, or certain messages could be given higher prominence than others. When applicable, the messages, being part of a local communication strategy, could be tailored to reflect the peculiarities of the local environment and audience alike.

Consortium members agreed upon the tone of voice being friendly, yet professional, educating vs. preaching, informative and engaging, passionate for seafood sustainability and committing to users' wellbeing. Stylistically, messages are conveyed comprehensively and rather informally, with occasional threads of subtle humor.

At its outset, the project managed to formulate its tagline as a branding slogan, reinforcing the key objectives it desires to be associated with, shown in the figure below (Figure 2).

Figure 2. SEA2SEE Slogan

In addition to conveying the multifaceted nature of SEA2SEE, the ultimate goal of the key messages is to trigger critical thinking and specific action of change to increased trust of European consumers in a more transparent and sustainable seafood sector, achieved through the wide adoption of an interactive and accessible blockchain based traceability technology. On the one hand, the messages deliver the competitive advantage of using SEA2SEE’s solution in the seafood value chain. On the other, they invite the public to become better informed about seafood sustainability related challenges.

Target audience	GP General Public VCA Value Chain Actors PM Policy Makers ECPA EC Public Authorities
Message 01	
Target audience	The innovative digital and data sharing tools SEA2SEE develops, contributes to sustainable seafood traceability and an increase of consumers’ trust in the sustainable seafood market in Europe.
GP	
Message 02	
Target audience	SEA2SEE digital tools support EU citizens in making informed decisions about seafood consumption.
GP	

Message 03

Target audience Active consumers' engagement leads to overcoming barriers in the social acceptance of sustainable seafood.

GP

Message 04

Target audience With its end-user app, SEA2SEE engages citizens as co-creators in the transition to a more resilient society, which contributes to consumer's preference shift towards sustainable seafood choices.

GP VCA PM

Message 05

Target audience SEA2SEE uses blockchain technology to ensure the trustworthiness of information about seafood production, bringing competitive advantage to its users.

VCA

Message 06

Target audience SEA2SEE innovative solution enables remote monitoring of numerous seafood production activities, thus obtaining transparency about aquaculture practices.

VCA aquaculture

Message 07

Target audience Gain transparency about fishing practices contributing to ocean conservation with SEA2SEE traceability technology.

VCA fisheries

Message 08

Target audience SEA2SEE solution meets the needs of a changing society towards sustainable behavior. Implementing our solution makes you a preferred seafood supplier.

VCA

Message 09

Target audience In concurrence with the Green Deal strategy and carbon neutrality by 2050, SEA2SEE provides the innovative technological means to support notified bodies for the certification auditing by digitalizing the process and therefore, reducing cost and required resources.

ECPA PM

Message 10

Target audience SEA2SEE raises European citizens' interest in the transparency of seafood activities, eventually leading to preference in consuming European products once full value chain digitized traceability becomes incorporated in an EU policy regulation, paving the way to a self-sufficient European seafood market.

ECPA GP VCA

Message 11

Target audience SEA2SEE's blockchain based seafood traceability platform supports, in the long run, EC in the development of an ecological production labeling policy and eco-labels integration in the final seafood product.

ECPA GP VCA

Figure 3. SEA2SEE Key Messages

SEAFOOD SUSTAINABILITY

Sustainability is a buzzword nowadays, used in a variety of situations and domains, and there seems to be a need to frame its meaning in the context of seafood and SEA2SEE project. One general definition proposed by FAO is that “sustainability is about meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”². From the seafood perspective, it could be claimed that seafood is sustainable when it is “caught or farmed in a way that ensures that future generations can still benefit from the world’s marine resources”³. Seafood Watch takes a wholesome approach to defining sustainable seafood operations as minimizing harmful environmental impacts, assuring good and fair working conditions, and supporting livelihoods and economic benefits throughout the entire supply chain⁴.

With its planned awareness raising campaigns about seafood traceability and sustainability, SEA2SEE project joins professionals, NGOs and governments in a conversation encouraging social action toward sustainable seafood consumption through empowering end-users with its co-creation mechanisms and consumer digital tool for sharing collected feedback, visualized and analyzed through a web-based app. Given the complexity of the notion of seafood sustainability, and the broad range of environmental and social aspects it entails, the Consortium considers important the development of a comprehensive definition embracing the multifaceted points of view of the actors across the value chain, which will be agreed upon by all members and used in future communications.

Communication key words and phrases:

- Blue Economy
- Ocean Literacy
- Seafood Economy
- Seafood Safety and Security
- Seafood Sustainability
- Seafood Traceability
- Seafood Quality

² FAO. 2019. *International Symposium on Fisheries Sustainability: Strengthening the science-policy nexus*, 18–21 November 2019. Rome

³ <https://www.cbi.eu/market-information/fish-seafood/certified-sustainable-seafood>

⁴ <https://www.seafoodwatch.org/seafood-basics/what-is-sustainable-seafood>

2.3. COMMUNICATION TOOLS AND CHANNELS

2.3.1. VISUAL IDENTITY

LOGO

The project's logo has been designed by the Consortium during the proposal phase of SEA2SEE and approved by all partners during the 1st Management Meeting in Rimini, Italy. It consists of the project's logotype, scripted in the Bahnschrift, applied to web headings as well, and bearing anatomy performing well on screen, and a pictograph with connected male and female human heads, expressing in a simplistic way the philosophy of blockchain technology connectivity but also gender diversity and balance employed by the project. The three waves under them link the technology to the water world and its creatures.

With its shades of blue, it associates the project with the calmness and purifying power of the ocean, while at the same time shapes its identity reliable and professional. The logo is an intrinsic component of the communication strategy of the project and must be included in the marketing materials across all channels, to strengthen and complement the communication of the project's goals, slogan and brand messages.

Figure 4. SEA2SEE Logo

Figure 5. Allowed logotype variations on logo colors' background

GRAPHIC CHARTER

In addition to the logo, a graphic charter has been created, outlining the standards and rules regarding the communication and dissemination of the SEA2SEE brand.

The purpose of the graphic charter is to provide uniformity and coherence to project's communication by supporting a consistent brand image, which ensures project's recognition and memorization by the relevant stakeholders.

All communication tools of SEA2SEE should be in compliance with the guidelines set out in the graphic charter, so that the main messages are properly conveyed to the various target groups, and always in harmony with its mission and objectives.

Figure 6. SEA2SEE Graphic Charter

In addition to the typography section, the graphic charter also includes the institutional palette, with allowed shades of the primary colors. Some secondary, accent colors are to be introduced later, inspired by the vibrancy of the underwater world, seafood products, cuisine and recipes.

Colors

Institutional palette

For Graphics, Design & typography . Similar shades are also accepted.

	#57C7D9	R: 87 G: 199 B: 217	C: 59% M: 0% Y: 15% K: 0%
	#0B90CC	R: 6 G: 144 B: 204	C: 79% M: 31% Y: 2% K: 0%
	#0B465B	R: 11 G: 70 B: 91	C: 95% M: 65% Y: 45% K: 32%

Similar shades:

	#5A7E8E				
	#89A2AE				
	#D1DADF				

How to display the acknowledgement of EU funding?

Display the EU emblem

Disclaimer

Please use the following disclaimer whenever using the funding logo:

- "Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

Guidance on how to display the acknowledgment of the EU funding as well as general Word and PowerPoint templates, with all branding requisites, are also part of the graphic charter, which makes it a convenient and easy-to-use reference tool when it comes to maintaining a consistent visual identity of the project.

Stationary

Word document - Title page

Word document - letterhead

Powerpoint - Title slide

Powerpoint - slides

Figure 7. SEA2SEE Graphic Charter

Both the Logo and Graphic Charter are available to all project partners in a shared collaborative internal SharePoint project's space.

2.3.2. PUBLIC RELATIONS

The relations of SEA2SEE with the general public and media are essential for the understanding of its mission and objective, hence, society-wide success. They are managed through the creation of attractive promotional and informational materials, such as the project brochure, online leaflet, video as well as regular press releases and an electronic newsletter. In addition to using SEA2SEE own media, the general project's overview, at first, and later, the main achievements of the project and related events are promoted via the local press, with the support of partner organizations' press offices and media contacts, whenever feasible.

SEA2SEE press kit is available for use to all partners and their communication needs in the project's SharePoint drive, while at the same time, it is easily accessible and downloadable by external users from the project's website, once launched (<https://sea2see.eu>), where all materials are published in English.

MARKETING MATERIALS – BROCHURE, LEAFLET, A5 FLYER, A0 POSTER, ROLLUP

The marketing and promotional materials within SAE2SEE are part of the concept for having an integrated marketing package, designed and prepared by Europroject (EP) and comprise in their core a print brochure, online leaflet and an A0 poster. Due to the high profile of stakeholder's engagement as an action in the project, the demand for promotional materials is considerable and a roll up for a trade show was designed in the first months after project's launch as well as an additional A5 flyer, for handing out conferences. Naturally, additional images, infographics and illustrations are adapted, designed and developed, for use on social media or offline, on an as needed basis or upon partners' request and with their input, in order to present the project, its objectives, expected results and benefits to end-users in a comprehensive manner to a variety of stakeholder profiles.

The materials are modifiable so that at the later, more results yielding phase of the project, they incorporate specific messages tailored to particular events and/or target audiences.

BROCHURE, LEAFLET AND A5 FLYER

The brochure of SEA2SEE was created as the project's factsheet basis for any subsequent informational derivatives for print or online communication and dissemination. The information contained therein presents a concise overview of the project, in a graphically attractive manner and relatively non-technical language, focused on the following: the need for the research and ambition of the project, its objectives, expected results as well as Consortium's composition, funding scheme, duration and contact information.

The brochure intends to reach out to all stakeholders identified to be part of SEA2SEE target audience. It has been designed in English and will be translated by partners to their national languages. It comes in two formats: a tri-fold material for print, which is to be distributed by project's partners during project events, national/international information days, demonstrations, visits, and an online leaflet with each partner's obligation to cooperate in its digital distribution among their respective network of contacts and media through sharing it on their own websites and social channels, as well as any other websites or social spaces of interested in the project institutions or organizations (neighborhood centers, consumer pages, blogs, professional associations, etc.) they have access to. More visual materials are planned to be developed later, with language and messages adapted to consumers and other specific audiences.

The online leaflet is modifiable for various digital media, easily customizable to serve each partner's needs, in a proper size so that it is easily sharable across online channels, and is multi-screen compatible.

PARTNERS

PROGRAMME: Horizon Europe (FARM2FORK)
TYPE OF ACTION: Innovation Action (IA)
DURATION: July 2022 – June 2026
CONSORTIUM: 14 partners from 6 EU countries
CALL: CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01
TOPIC ID: HORIZON-CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01-10
BUDGET: 5 418 730 EUR
EU CONTRIBUTION: 4 392 345 EUR

CONTACT US

PROJECT COORDINATOR:
Carlos Mazorra (SmartWater)
carlos.mazorra@smartwaterplanet.com

GENERAL CONTACT:
contact@sea2see.eu

- [sea2see.eu](https://www.sea2see.eu)
- [sea2see-project](#)
- [sea2see_project](#)
- [sea2seeproject](#)
- [@Sea2seeProject](#)

COORDINATOR:
SMARTWATER PLANET SL (SmartWater)

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Environmental and food safety policies in the European Union aim to ensure more sustainable, inclusive, safe and healthy seafood production and consumption in Europe. A number of challenges continues to impede the achievement of the desired level of transparency and traceability of seafood products as the European seafood markets can still be characterized with a high level of unsustainable fishing and farming practices.

Sea2See project's main goal is to make actors with sustainable seafood practices more visible to consumers in order to give them a competitive advantage.

“The interactive and accessible blockchain based platform that the Sea2See project is developing, will contribute to significantly increase Trust, Transparency and Traceability of the European Seafood Sector throughout the value chain, and to implement societal and sectoral strategies for co-creation, communication and awareness-raising about the benefits of sustainably fished and farmed nutritious seafood, from the producer to the end consumer”

Carlos Mazorra, SEA2SEE Coordinator, R&D and Innovation Director of Smart Water Planet SL

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only, and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

KEY CHALLENGES

- Inconsistent information about seafood products: species, origin, fishing gear, feed, welfare issues, production methods and parameters such as water quality, processing and transportation. Most seafood products have a more complex history than what their legal origin displays. Transparency is mission possible with digitization.
- Unsustainable practices such as the use of unselective gear with high by-catch and discards, undersized fish and invertebrates catch, illegal and unregulated fishing, fraud unaccountability;
- Lack of digitalization and tailored software tools for seafood products traceability. Seafood traceability requires innovative and cost-efficient approaches. The main challenge of linking clearly sustainability and traceability of EU seafood lies in the ability for real-time assessment of sustainability indicators across value chain actors.

KEY INFORMATION

PROGRAMME: Horizon Europe (FARM2FORK)

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CONTACT US:
contact@sea2see.eu

VISIT OUR WEBSITE:
<http://sea2see.eu/>

WE ARE SOCIAL:

[sea2see-project](#)

[sea2seeproject](#)

[sea2see_project](#)

[@Sea2seeProject](#)

	OBJECTIVES	EXPECTED RESULTS
<p>Environmental and food safety policies in the European Union aim to ensure more sustainable, inclusive, safe and healthy seafood production and consumption in Europe. A number of challenges continues to impede the achievement of the desired level of transparency and traceability of seafood products as the European seafood markets can still be characterized with a high level of unsustainable fishing and farming practices.</p> <p>Sea2See project's main goal is to make actors with sustainable seafood practices more visible to consumers in order to give them a competitive advantage.</p>	<p>Sea2See's main goal is to build consumer trust and acceptance of sustainably fished or farmed seafood in Europe. This will be achieved with two types of action:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Development and demonstration of an innovative end-to-end blockchain traceability model throughout the seafood value chain Implementation of societal and sectoral strategies for co-creation, communication and awareness raising about the benefits of sustainably fished or farmed nutritious seafood <p>Sea2See will significantly increase the consumption potential since the consumers, in part, will be engaged through participatory strategies showing how web-based and digital tools can provide trustworthy traceability information. The objectives are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a co-creation approach to sustainable seafood transparency and traceability Leverage a set of awareness raising and educational practices to increase sustainable seafood consumption Develop a blockchain deployment model for seafood industry-specific traceability data collection Demonstrate the feasibility and advantages of the Sea2See blockchain model Develop a standardized Life Cycle Assessment framework for identifying and quantifying the major sources of environmental impact 	<p>Traceability blockchain data deployment model – web app accessing real-time shared data blockchain and data collection tool for professional end-users.</p> <p>Data flow funnel capturing aquaculture production data to storing transformed data in blockchain, and development of data management software within the deployed cloud architecture.</p> <p>Blockchain consumer engagement tools, such as consumer app connected via QR-code to shared life-cycle data on the end-consumer product, with integration of consumer feedback collection.</p> <p>Value Chain Stakeholders Engagement Strategy – applies geographically and stakeholder tailored co-creation methodology.</p> <p>Tools and customized campaigns for sustainable seafood consumption – QR codes linking to MOOC, Youtube, virtual sustainable seafood cookbook, etc.</p> <p>Life Cycle Sustainability and environmental impact assessment complemented by guidelines for replication, scalability and knowledge transfer.</p> <p>Demonstrators Toolkit – case studies with lessons learned to be created as datasets of generated by the project data.</p>

Figure 8. SEA2SEE Brochure and A5 Flyer

A0 POSTER AND ROLLUP

A large format poster for print to be used for promoting the project at conferences, fairs, trade shows, exhibitions and synergy events. The design is in synch with the established visual identity of SEA2SEE and builds upon the initially made rollup presenting the project at Aquaculture 2022 Conference with just a catch phrase, recognized later as SEA2SEE's brand slogan. The poster could be customized to different print sizes and content variations depending on the context of its use.

Figure 9. SEA2SEE A0 Poster and Aquaculture Conference 2022 Rollup

PRESS RELEASE

Press releases are the means by which important project news, milestones and achievements are communicated to the media and wider public. As WP7 leader, EP, and SmartWater as coordinator, draft the press releases based on partners' inputs regarding achieved project's results and significant developments. Each press release is published on the website to be either picked up by relevant media or distributed by partners' public affairs offices to local press. At least three (3) notices for the press are to be released during the timeframe of the project (M7, M24 and M48). An image of the first one, which is accessible from SEA2SEE website, is presented below (Fig. 10).

Figure 10. SEA2SEE Press Release

E-NEWSLETTER

The electronic newsletter of the project is considered a powerful, high-conversion and cost-effective marketing tool. In addition to spreading the word about SEA2SEE, it contributes to building a database of contacts interested in the project results that can become part of an overall stakeholder engagement database, even for future projects.

SEA2SEE newsletter is sent to subscribers biannually throughout the duration of the project, the first one starting in M8. It will include project's overview, reports on first conducted meetings, important announcements regarding social media and the launch of the website as well as partners' presentation. The content of the subsequent issues will take into account things as follows:

- events regarding project's progress and results;
- dates, details, stories regarding project related conferences, meetings, webinars or publications;
- project-related news, new initiatives, liaisons;
- synergies with related projects, programs and initiatives.

All partners are encouraged to participate in generating content for the newsletters. Europroject (EP) is responsible for coordinating the work, collecting contributions from members, editing and distributing the newsletter via a MailChimp account. In order to reach the maximum desired audience size, the Consortium partners are invited to further distribute the newsletters to their professional contacts, preparing grounds for potential collaborations regarding results exploitation and/or joint applications in next projects.

Everybody can subscribe free of charge to the newsletter from the project's website where it is published too, in downloadable format.

Compliance

The SEA2SEE newsletter will be designed in full compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The email footer will display the sender's address and will offer an unsubscribe/opt out button. The first newsletter is under preparation.

Figure 11. SEA2SEE Newsletter - concept

VIDEO

Two short videos will be produced by EP post M6, in a visually appealing and easily understandable way for an audience of non-scientists. The objective of the first video is an overall introduction of the project and the new technologies it develops regarding the improvement of seafood traceability. The second video is expected in M42 and it will focus on promoting the project's achievements and outcomes, and raising social interest in the utilization of the technological solution SEA2SEE develops. The videos will be published on the project's YouTube channel, shared on the website, social media and through the newsletter, on partners' websites and digital media, and will be played at events, whenever feasible.

OUR VIDEOS

STAY TUNED FOR SEA2SEE VIDEOS HERE

Figure 12. Link of SEA2SEE videos appearing on website's homepage

Videos are an essential communication tool which is becoming increasingly popular and outranking the other forms of communication in terms of audience reach and engagement rate. In addition to the voiceover, the videos will have subtitles so that the content is accessible and comprehended by everyone and anywhere.

2.3.3. WEBSITE

SEA2SEE website is the main hub for all communication activities of the project. The SEA2SEE domain was acquired in August 2022 (<https://SEA2SEE.eu>) and the website is expected to be brought live by the end of December. It is fully designed and developed by EP as WP7 leader, in collaboration with SmartWater, as coordinator, and the rest of the project partners. The website is updated with the input from all partners and maintained throughout the project's lifespan, to include 2 years after its end. It provides the latest news and findings in SEA2SEE and ensures access to the knowledge and data accumulated during the project to Consortium members, key stakeholders and the public at large even beyond the timeframe of the project.

The website of SEA2SEE appears in all promotional materials, both print and online, and constitutes a space for regularly communicating outputs, achieved milestones, and publishing official results.

The website aims to achieve the following objectives:

- Build awareness and understanding about project's mission, work activities, objectives and results;

- Ensure visibility of the project;
- Enhance the impact of the project through timely and accessible dissemination of its results;
- Enable effective communication between the project and external stakeholders, media and the public;
- Wide promotion of the project through easy access to the portfolio of informational and branding materials;
- Enable synergies and engagement with similar projects, programs and initiatives through relevant content, a prerequisite in itself for sharing and exchanging knowledge and best practices;
- Facilitate the exploitation of the project's results.

Its sections include information about the project, overview of the Consortium, description of the project expected results (including public deliverables once approved), demonstration sites overview, news and events and subject matter related short articles (blog posts), project e-newsletter, video, communication kit for the media and social media links. For information protection reasons, the website cannot accommodate a link to partners' Intranet space for the time being. Below are some images showing website's work in progress:

Figure 13. SEA2SEE website pages samples

The website is described in detail in deliverable **D7.1 Project Website and Social Media**.

For project awareness building and maximizing the dissemination impact, project partners are continuously encouraged to make reference to the project’s website on their own websites too.

2.3.4. SOCIAL MEDIA

Social networks are the place where we connect with our audience most, the place where the conversation happens, and when used strategically, they become an efficient tool for reaching a variety of stakeholder groups. The dynamic nature of the information exchange there turns them into a suitable host to real-time information sharing, announcements of important events, synergy actions, reports, briefs as well as live streaming of webinars, speeches, interviews, etc. In this sense, social media contributes directly to the following objectives:

- Build awareness and increase visibility;
- Trigger interest in the topic and subsequently support it through sharing news with both expert and non-expert audience;
- Multiply the impact through engagement in relevant subject specific community groups;
- Build an expert voice by commenting and sharing opinion on trending topics and issues in the field;
- Promote knowledge, activities, benefits and outcomes generated during and after the project's lifespan;
- Enhance project positioning through engine search, image search, local search;
- Start a conversation about seafood traceability with the target audience by keeping it engaged with two-way interactions through surveys, polls, public discussions and invitations to project's events

Due to the quick turnover of news in the digital social environment, it is essential for the project's communication success to post content regularly vs. ad hoc or sporadic activity. For this reason, a Content Publishing Calendar is created for project's partners to plan their content contributions for both social media and website, with the aim to post own content once a week and relevant curated content generated by other users/contact once a week. Social Media activity envisions 8 posts a month.

SEA2SEE Consortium has decided to use for social networking in the beginning LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook and Twitter. LinkedIn is the professional social network of SEA2SEE for establishing connections with similar projects, creating events, joining professional groups and conversations, cross-sharing news and important project information from its other channels. The project's name in LinkedIn is [@Sea2see-project](#). Given the significance of stakeholders' engagement and the large communication effort it entails, Instagram and Facebook are the next two social media channels that the project relies upon to bring visibility to its goals and objectives and to gain followers, friends, fans and supporters. The style we embrace there is more direct, informal, even friendlier. The nature of these channels predisposes to sharing lots of visuals, infographics and videos. In Instagram the project appears as [@sea2see_project](#) while in Facebook it could be found as [@sea2seeproject](#).

Twitter is considered as one-to-many broadcast networks, with a conversation pace much faster than any other social media. A diverse community of scientific, research and business organizations hang out there, either institutionally or individually, which also makes it a good medium for promoting SEA2SEE news and results, especially in hashtag campaigns and as threaded content. The handle of SEA2SEE in Twitter is [@Sea2seeProject](#). Lastly, SEA2SEE will have a YouTube channel as well, to share the wealth of video content that is to be produced, especially during the fishery and aquaculture demonstration phases of the project. The YouTube channel hosts the two project videos as well and is created and managed by UAVR.

Figure 14. LinkedIn Account of SEA2SEE

Figure 15. SEA2SEE Facebook page

Figure 16. SEA2SEE Instagram account

Figure 17. SEA2SEE Twitter Account

The social media accounts of SEA2SEE are managed by Europroject (EP), with the assistance of the rest of the members and task leaders in WP7, Ethic Ocean and Vitagora. Each month partners are invited to provide content inputs for the following month. Additionally, they are regularly reminded to follow and share the accounts, re-post on their personal and institutional profiles as well as to recommend correlated organizations, projects, initiatives and events that the project can follow in order to build a solid network of stakeholders and induce higher engagement rates through a dialogue.

The information posted on the social media accounts is done in a consistent and coherent manner, using the defined above (cf. 2.2. Key Messages) messages, project's keywords and phrases as hashtags as well as the appropriate tagging of partners, collaborators and EC authorities for greater visibility.

LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook and Twitter icons are integrated in the footer of the website with a call to action to visitors to follow the project. It is planned to add social media buttons in the News section of the website, allowing readers to easily share the published content, such as events, news, articles, pictures and videos. Managing four social media accounts is quite demanding in terms of time and human resources, which could result in unhealthy social pages. For this reason, after the first twelve months of presence there, a thorough analysis of the insights will be conducted to assess the success rates in terms of engagement rates and set KPIs. Social accounts not performing to the expected metrics might be closed.

2.3.5. OTHER

The rich variety of promotional tools designed in the beginning of the project as part of its integrated marketing communication includes also several marketing products addressing children, such as children science games, and eco-touristic seafood consumption through dedicated marketing information materials distributed in restaurants, aiming to raise people's awareness about the benefits of seafood consumption, sustainable seafood consumption and cultural heritage related seafood. The design and development of these materials and the concept for their distribution is led by SUBMON, who have rich experience in this regard.

Publications

Publications regarding SEA2SEE significant results and outputs are essential for meeting the project's objectives. In addition, partners are committed to present papers at international conferences and in high impact peer review scientific journals, giving priority to open access editions to increase visibility and quotation rates.

Joint papers and other publications on the digitalization as a way to achieve full seafood traceability, and on stakeholders' engagement strategies to overcome barriers, potentially co-written with colleagues from related EU projects, would not only disseminate the results internationally but would enhance the esteem of the partnership and unambiguously demonstrate the collaboration drive of the EU-funded research and innovation for stronger European economies and technological and innovation progress, improving citizens lives.

Keeping track of the number of own generated publications but also of such that quote project's authors or refer to the project's outcomes is an important value for a later-on assessment of the dissemination impact of SEA2SEE.

Events

Throughout the project's lifetime, the Consortium members are expected to attend a considerable number of events related to the subject of SEA2SEE, either as participants or organizers. The Communication and Dissemination Plan focuses mostly on the external activities given the internal coordination and Consortium meetings are considered mostly a management tool rather than means for communication and dissemination of project's goals, objectives and results to its users.

Some types of events that are meant to be organized and attended by the partners are international conferences, fairs, trade shows and exhibitions, workshops for the general public, workshops with brokerage events at the final conference of the project as well as coordinated joint and synergy events with related projects and initiatives that are elaborated upon in **D7.4 Synergy Plan**. In the post COVID-19 times, it should also be taken into account, that events might be in-presence, online or hybrid, each with their own interactional requirements and marketing specifics.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

The strategic communication, dissemination and exploitation approach adopted within the project is aligned with the general and specific objectives of the respective activity, with messages, channels and formats, tailored to the relevant target groups, local context and timing. Table 1 highlights a summarized version of the proposed communication and dissemination strategy.

Besides responding to task T7.1 and T7.2, the implementation of the current CD Plan (D7.2) is linked to T7.3 *Communication and Dissemination Campaigns*, which aims to promote the project and disseminate its results to key stakeholders and the general public in accordance with the delineated activities in the plan and commences at M6. It is led by Ethic Ocean and is further connected to D7.3 *Report on the Communication and Dissemination Activities*.

3.1. COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

As already stated in the previous sections, the main objective of SEA2SEE is to significantly increase consumer trust and acceptance of sustainably fished and farmed seafood in Europe through the development and demonstration of an innovative end-to-end blockchain traceability model throughout

the seafood value chain and the implementation of societal and sectoral strategies for co-creation, communication and awareness raising about the benefits of sustainably fished or farmed nutritious seafood.

The communication campaigns are planned to entirely support this objective by targeting most of all the general public. Besides their underlining goal of broadly promoting project's objectives, preliminary results and any other achievements, they support an expected shift toward more sustainable practices. By highlighting to Europeans the added health, economic and environmental value of consuming sustainably fished or farmed seafood, they are likely to transition from casual consumers to sustainable consumers. Communication campaigns further facilitate the establishing of synergies with external bodies such as national/international associations, projects and initiatives.

The project will use its visual identity, popular science articles, its website and social media, videos and promotional material to show how web-based and digital tools can provide traceability information that can be trusted. As mentioned before, beneficiary institutions and individuals involved in SEA2SEE act as ambassadors and interpreters of the project's results and contribute to stakeholders' engagement in the process through participatory strategies and the right messaging. The following activities are planned to be implemented to increase the visibility of the project towards all relevant stakeholders, with special focus on consumers.

The first communication wave of SEA2SEE employs as its vehicle the **website and communication toolbox** for a general introduction of SEA2SEE, its ambition correlated with defining the societal need for the developed technological novelty, the main approaches and methodology involved, specific objectives, expected results and overall impact across the whole spectrum of life. The main goal of this first wave is hence, brand awareness but also sparking curiosity in what is next. The second and the third communication waves are designed to gradually move down stakeholders to the middle and bottom of the marketing funnel of the project – from engagement and consideration, with harder focus on dissemination activities, to the adoption and advocacy phase, with communication activities targeting predominantly the exploitation possibilities within SEA2SEE.

Information on SEA2SEE is actively posted on its social media platforms to enable a boost of project's coverage in online and offline media by other similar projects and the Internet in general. Online promotional campaigns and ad campaigns are launched throughout the duration of the project to increase visibility among the targeted groups and ensure high participation on the initiatives carried out by the project, including capacity building.

Social media campaigns in Instagram, Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter will be organized to give SEA2SEE relevant, direct, and immediate connection with stakeholder groups during the different phases of the project. Some suggested campaigns are presented in the table below:

Campaign's name	Campaign's goal	Campaign's content	When
<i>Discover SEA2SEE</i>	Awareness raising Sparking curiosity in SEA2SEE next steps	Project context (including explanation of key notions), project goals, project organization and timeline, who is who in the project.	M6-M12
<i>Get into the traceability technology</i>	Awareness raising Dissemination of partners efforts and first project results	Project first results Project tangible outputs WPs leaders' feedback (articles) Project coordinator feedback (A word by the Coordinator)	M18-M24
<i>For a more transparent, competitive and sustainable seafood market</i>	Awareness raising Dissemination of demonstration/pilot sites results Focus on exploitation opportunities	Project concrete results Project added value for the whole seafood value chain actors, including policy makers, public authorities and investors.	M36-M48 and after

Table 2. Suggested social media communication and dissemination campaigns

The first communication campaign targeted at the general public is organized to promote the project in conjunction with the Food EXPO 2023 – March (cf. Table 5). This will be accompanied by an intensive social media presence for a number of days and a press release to attract media attention.

Horizon Europe social media guide for EU funded R&I projects will be adopted in the implementation of the above-described campaigns, including the search tool for EU related projects and initiatives for mentions and tagging in order to boost visibility and broaden the reach. The proposed campaigns will have a duration of 4 to 6 weeks.

Keywords and hashtags to be used in social media:

Blue Economy
Ocean Literacy
Seafood Economy
Seafood Safety and Security
Sea/food Sustainability
Seafood Traceability
Seafood Quality
Seafood consumption
Green Deal
Low carbon footprint seafood
Sustainable fishing practices
Sustainable aquaculture
Sealife biodiversity
Sustainable seafood chain
Stakeholders engagement
Consumer awareness
Blockchain technology
Climate change
European project
SEA2SEEproject

Emojis: seafood, technology, people

SEA2SEE communication strategy wishes to broadly spread project's activities and outcomes and engage consumers as informed creators and users of a sustainable seafood market. Each of the identified stakeholder audiences – consumers (including vulnerable groups), academics, producers, private sector and media – are informed through a variety of online and offline communication activities about the project's progress and opportunities to interact. Communication of progress will be further divided to information of general interest and information targeting specific stakeholder groups. Press releases and articles are published in field-relevant magazines, online and traditional media, with a preference to local outlets, which are more popular among the local communities of consumers. SEA2SEE will also make use of the project members' own online communication tools including websites, newsletters and social media, in order to engage local audiences in their local languages.

In the Monitoring and Evaluation Section, the CD plan features some quantitative KPIs regarding the communication activities (number of visitors to the webpage and social media, number of talks/presentations, videos uploaded, number of events, attendance to public engagement events, etc.) to monitor the progress and efficiency of the plan. In the case of low impact data detected at an early stage, pertinent corrective actions will be set up like adapting the messages, tone of voice and language, frequency and medium of posts and publications. The monitoring plan includes also periodic partners' reports on results of communication actions.

3.2. DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The dissemination activities begin with the advancement of the project towards its first achieved results that benefit the EU citizens or transfer knowledge to stakeholders that can best make use of it. All partners act as multipliers, contributing to the dissemination of project results within their networks, thus making them available for future research, interdisciplinary interactions and uptake by specific audiences, including but not limited to: scientific community, seafood value chain actors, policymakers, non-governmental organizations, public authorities.

The specific objectives of the current dissemination effort are defined as follows:

- Inform about project results as they pertain to blockchain based technology, seafood traceability, sustainable seafood consumption, blue economy, climate change and ocean literacy groups, regulatory and decision-making authorities, food security related institutions;
- Spark interest in SEA2SEE as a secure technological solution adding business and social value to the short seafood supply chain in Europe;
- Publish about and promote the significant technological results delivered by the project;
- Understand and protect intellectual property rights during collaborations with industry participants;
- Raise awareness about the wider benefits of adopting SEA2SEE solution, beyond its original focus;
- Maximise general public visibility of project's results and achievements;

SEA2SEE dissemination activities and events are accomplished with the active contribution of all partners in the timeframe of the project. The main channels and tools to achieve dissemination objectives are presented below. The activities essentially focus on mobilizing stakeholders and providing a reliable, smooth, and efficient knowledge transfer of the SEA2SEE outcomes to end-users and the other defined target groups. To review and measure the effectiveness of the dissemination strategy, suitable evaluation mechanisms are applied along with regular adaptations of the CD plan.

3.2.1. ONLINE AND OFFLINE MEDIA

Social media campaigns – dissemination campaigns have the objective to trigger deeper interest in stakeholders and other interested parties with engaging with project's results. The second and third social media campaigns, described in more detail above (Table 2), follow: *Get into the traceability technology* (M18 – M24) – focused on disseminating relevant public project's results and prompt stakeholders' engagement. *For a more transparent, competitive and sustainable seafood market* (M36 – M48 and after) – aims to share application case studies, popular articles, blog posts to target industry, investors, public institutions with potential exploitation opportunities. As a follow up activity to this campaign, a selected group of users of SEA2SEE "blockchain-based platform could be interviewed to get their feedback about its added value to their business and turn them into engaging success stories, published in social media and other digital channels.

Before posting on social media, prior notice of planned publication disseminating project results or know-how content is required to be sent to the Coordinator, SmartWater and WP7 lead, EP. In case of objections to the planned publication, the publication is not permitted.

Continuous dissemination to the media includes at least **3 press releases**, also shared on SEA2SEE's digital social accounts. **Popular articles** are planned to be published in sector-specific blogs or magazines with a preference to local outlets, which are more popular among local communities and consumers. A list of magazines, online media and general media per each partner's country has been developed and will be used for planning and tracking purpose by each project partner.

All partners will act as multipliers, contributing to the dissemination of project results within their networks.

Some online and offline media included in that list are presented in the table below:

Country	Media's name
France	Le marin Linéaires L'Autre Cuisine
Greece	Alieftika nea Agrotypos Ambrosia
Portugal	Jornal da Economia e do Mar Ambiente Magazine Publituris Hotelaria
Spain	Acuicultura de España El escarabajo verde En la cocina http://mispeces.com/

Table 3. Indicative, non-exhaustive list of magazines, on-line media and general media per each project partner country

A **newsletter** starting in M8 until the end of the project is sent to the pool of interested subscribers generated from the subscription form on the website to keep them posted about the latest news and developments. The public deliverables of SEA2SEE as well as any other materials created by the Consortium partners to bring visibility to project's outputs and achievements are published on the **website** and openly accessible.

One opportunity which should be taken into account with the advancement of work is the generation of a success story that is to be published on own channels, reposted on partners' websites and further promoted via some of the European Commission's free-of-charge channels: Cordis Results in Brief,

CORDIScovery podcasts, HE Mission boards, Horizon Magazine or during events such as the R&I Days, subject to coordination with the Project Officer.

If despite the best effort for disseminating the results no uptake happens one year after the end of the project, the exploitable results will be made visible on the Horizon Result Platform.

3.2.2. PUBLICATIONS

Publishing about project's development and the results it entails is essential for meeting the project's dissemination objectives among the scientific community and fellow researchers. Partners are engaged to present the project results at relevant national, European and international events and prepare publications for scientific journals. At least **4 peer-reviewed publications** of significant results in high impact, open access scientific journals are planned.

Journal / Magazine	Description	Impact Factor
Trends in Food Science and Technology	<i>Trends in Food Science & Technology</i> is one of the premier international peer-reviewed journals publishing critical reviews and commentaries of current technology, food science and human nutrition. Its role is to fill the gap between the specialized primary journals and general trade magazines by focusing on the most promising new research developments and their current and potential food industry applications in a readable, scientifically rigorous way. www.sciencedirect.com/journal/trends-in-food-science-and-technology	12.563
Food Control	Food control is an official scientific journal of the European Federation of Food Science and Technology (EFFoST) and the International Union of Food Science and Technology (IUFoST). Food Control is an international journal that provides essential information for those involved in food safety and process control. Food Control covers areas that relate to food process control or to food safety of human foods www.sciencedirect.com/journal/food-control	5.548
Marine Policy	Marine Policy is the leading journal of ocean policy studies. Submissions to Marine Policy must contribute to the formulation and understanding of marine policy, and must be of interest to a broad audience of academics, stakeholders and officials. Marine Policy offers researchers, analysts, stakeholders and policy-makers a unique combination of analyses in the principal social science disciplines relevant to the formulation of marine policy. www.journals.elsevier.com/marine-policy	4.315
Fisheries Research	Fisheries Research is an international journal on fisheries science, fishing technology and fisheries management. The scope covers fisheries in salt, brackish and freshwater systems, and all aspects of associated ecology,	2.422

	<p>environmental aspects of fisheries, and economics. Both theoretical and practical papers are acceptable, including laboratory and field experimental studies relevant to fisheries.</p> <p>www.sciencedirect.com/journal/fisheries-research</p>	
Journal of Food Engineering	<p>Journal of Food Engineering publishes original research and review papers on any subject at the interface between food and engineering, particularly those of relevance to industry, including:</p> <p>Engineering properties of foods, food physics and physical chemistry; processing, measurement, control, packaging, storage and distribution; engineering aspects of the design and production of novel foods and of food service and catering; design and operation of food processes, plant and equipment; economics of food engineering, including the economics of alternative processes.</p> <p>www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-food-engineering</p>	5.354
PLOS ONE	<p>PLOS ONE is an inclusive journal community working together to advance science for the benefit of society, now and in the future.</p> <p>The research published is multidisciplinary and, often, interdisciplinary. PLOS ONE accepts research in over two hundred subject areas across science, engineering, medicine, and the related social sciences and humanities. They evaluate submitted manuscripts on the basis of methodological rigor and high ethical standards, regardless of perceived novelty.</p> <p>journals.plos.org/plosone/s/journal-information</p>	3.24
Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems	<p>Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems publishes rigorously peer-reviewed research on: sustainably achieving global food security. Led by an outstanding Editorial Board of international experts, this open-access journal is at the forefront of disseminating and communicating scientific knowledge and impactful discoveries, both basic and applied, to academics, policy-makers, practitioners, industry and the public worldwide. The journal welcomes contributions from across the natural and social sciences (including the critical social sciences) as well as interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary work.</p> <p>www.frontiersin.org/journals/sustainable-food-systems</p>	5.005

Table 4. Indicative, non-exhaustive list of European and International related journals

Open Access

By following the ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’ principle, SEA2SEE Consortium ensures the application of an open science strategy in compliance with Horizon Europe’s guidelines and aimed at open cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge and tools. The project aims to benefit from the involvement of all relevant knowledge actors. SEA2SEE partners will ensure provision of immediate open access to scientific publications whenever necessary while safeguarding their legitimate interests and intellectual property rights. Therefore, trusted repositories and platforms are used, such as openAIRE (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe), European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Open Research Europe (ORE) to grant access to the publications and bibliographic metadata in conformity with the European Commission requirements. Since high impact publications would be of priority, the Consortium aims to ensure immediate full Open Access to those scientific publications, as

well. Research data will be deposited in national repositories, such as RCAAP for example, although other solutions such as ZENODO, are also explored and a SEA2SEE account on ZENODO will be created.

Partners are encouraged to speak about the project in public venues and to publish results obtained throughout the project after ensuring IP protection of exploitable results, and except when this goes against their legitimate interests, as foreseen in the Grant Agreement. In preparing speaking material and/or publications partners focus on their own work and results.

The confidentiality obligations set out in Section 10 of the Consortium Agreement apply to all dissemination activities as far as sensitive information is involved. Prior notice of any planned publication or presentation containing technical or know-how content is given to the partners at least 45 calendar days before the proposed date for publication. Objections to the planned publication are made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the partner or partners proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no justified objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is approved.

All partners have the legal obligation to properly acknowledge the funding received by the European Union on all communication and publications. An important element with this regard is the European Union emblem and the funding statement, which must be displayed prominently on all printed and digital products, websites, social media channels and other communication products. This is further elaborated in Section 5. *EC Acknowledgment Requirements*.

3.2.3. EVENTS

- ***Capacity building workshops*** are organized within the framework of the project to train value chain actors on the novel digital technology developed via SEA2SEE.
- ***One workshop with brokerage events*** - carried out as part of SEA2SEE final conference (M48). As incentive for exploitation, it targets professionals from the seafood value chain, R&D and end-users aiming to provide information and exchange on state-of-the-art solutions developed within the project and the sector as a whole.
- ***SEA2SEE final conference*** - to coincide with the third communication wave and summarizing the accomplished activities, sharing and promoting the results and fostering the uptake of the developed technological solutions.
- At least ***6 presentations*** by key project representatives at selected scientific conferences, congresses, symposia, exhibitions, trade shows, fairs to facilitate the wide exposure of the project's outputs.
- ***International Conferences and Events*** - a non-exhaustive, suggestive list of relevant European and international events for the 2022 – 2026 period is presented in the table below:

Name	Description	Link
Aquaculture America 2023	The largest aquaculture trade show in the Western Hemisphere and one of the largest anywhere in the world with nearly 200 booths.	www.was.org/meeting/code/AA2023
Aquaculture Europe	Annual meeting of the European Aquaculture Society (EAS) that brings together all the aquaculture stakeholders, academia, producers, suppliers, associations and investors. Mostly focused on the European sector but not exclusively.	www.aquaeas.eu/events/future-eas-events
Aquaculture UK	The UK's largest trade show for the aquaculture community.	https://aquacultureuk.com/
European Maritime Day (EMD)	The most important event at the European level for the maritime community to meet, discuss and plan joint actions on maritime affairs and sustainable blue economy.	https://maritime-day.ec.europa.eu/
World Aquaculture and Fisheries conference	WAC conference was established as a knowledge-sharing platform to highlight the possibility and distinctiveness of small-scale artisanal fisheries and aquaculture, as well as the advantage that can be gained by fostering collaborations and cooperation with fish farmers and workers, as well as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).	www.worldaquacultureconference.com
ICES Annual Science Conference	Conference organized by the ICES (International Council for the Exploration of the Sea) which provides an annual overview of the status of the fish stocks in the Northeast Atlantic and Baltic Sea.	www.ices.dk
World Fisheries Congress	Every four years delegates from around the world meet to exchange ideas and perspectives about new research, emerging issues, scientific breakthroughs, and governance related to fisheries science, industry, conservation, and management.	https://wfc2024.fisheries.org/

SIRHA	A premium trade fair for the food service, catering and food industry sectors. I	www.sirha-lyon.com/en
Food Expo 2023	The largest Food & Beverage trade show in Southeast Europe and one of the most significant of its kind internationally.	https://foodexpo.gr/en/
Seafood Expo Global/Seafood Processing Global	This is the global seafood marketplace, serving industry professionals and buyers from all corners of the supply chain and world.	www.seafoodexpo.com/global/

Table 5. SEA2SEE suggested events and conferences

3.2.4. NETWORKING

As comprehensively elaborated in the Synergy Plan (**D7.4**), synergy building and networking activities enhance the dissemination of project results to a broader interest audience, increase the visibility of the members and foster learning from, and building upon, other projects' findings and experiences. Some initiatives seen as beneficial for cooperation and extended dissemination of SEA2SEE outcomes are for example, Horizon Europe Missions, H2020 and HE similar projects, the European Technology Platforms (ETPs) and European Technology & Innovation Platforms (ETIP) recognized as suitable niches to present the technology achievements of SEA2SEE, as they are visited by the target stakeholder groups. For a detailed outline of these as well as other synergy and collaborative opportunities, refer to the Synergy Plan (**D7.4**)

DISSEMINATION AFTER PROJECT'S END

SEA2SEE social media accounts and website, including the private partners' space will keep being functional 2 years after the project concludes, to ensure access to the acquired knowledge and accumulated data. The project data will also be available in selected and consolidated repositories (cf. Data Management Plan). The synergies established during the timeframe of SEA2SEE can expand beyond its length through an ongoing interaction with the identified related organizations, networks, initiatives and similar EU-funded projects (Task 7.4), enabling a robust stakeholder community with entities having an interest in using SEA2SEE blockchain solutions, cooperating on a range of future joint dissemination actions, or up taking SEA2SEE results to common funding applications or future technological collaborations. With regard to the joint application process, partners will focus on compiling a joint Research and Innovation (R&I) agenda to discuss and plan the endeavor a year before the project ends. The final outcomes of the joint R&I agenda are expected to be operationalized in new projects, expanding on the approaches, technologies and outcomes of SEA2SEE.

3.3. INITIAL EXPLOITATION

The exploitation of SEA2SEE technological solutions will be described in a separate Exploitation Plan (T6.4) allowing for the large-scale exploitability of the project results and contributing to the sustainability and replicability of the project. Each Key Exploitable Result of SEA2SEE would enjoy a tailored to it exploitation strategy with regard to further research activities, development and/or commercialization of products and/or processes, creating and providing services, standardization, policies for improvement and last but not least, addressing various environmental, societal and economic issues.

In brief, the exploitation strategy comprises the following structural components:

- Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Management Strategy,
- Exploitation Strategies
- Feasibility Study

4. MONITORING AND EVALUATION

Review measures and evaluation mechanisms are required to keep the dissemination and communication plan in vigor. Its effectiveness is assessed against the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) set in the Grant Agreement, and whenever serious discrepancies are ascertained, necessary adaptations are made to the DC Plan in order to keep abreast of the project’s objectives successful accomplishment.

4.1. KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

Per SEA2SEE Grant Agreement, the project has defined the following communication and dissemination KPIs:

Channel/Medium	Purpose	KPIs	Main Target Group
Website (M6) One-way communication	Main informational hub about the project; Educates about the research topic through blog posts; Disseminates findings; Features developed solutions;	8 000 website visitors throughout project’s lifetime; kept active 2 years post project’s end.	All

	Provides contact information for interested stakeholders.		
Social Media (M3) Two-way communication	Directly connects with target audience; Informs and disseminates results; Real time information exchange; Interactive; All partners contribute.	> 500 followers; 2 social media accounts	All
Press releases (M6) One-way communication	Brand awareness; Raise Interest in project and its results; Highlight business uptake opportunities.	at least 3 press releases ; 2 media mentions per press release.	Media and general public
Newsletter (M6) Could be two-way	Informs, promotes, disseminates results;	Bi-annual ; >1000 subscribers by the end of the project	Interested stakeholders through subscription form
Articles One-way communication	Inform, promote, educate ;	At least 3 popular science articles	Specific Stakeholder Groups
Scientific publications One-way communication	Dissemination of significant results in high impact open access scientific journals	4 peer-reviewed publications; 50 specialized stakeholders reached	Scientific Community ; Policy makers.
Presentations Two-way communication	Wide exposure of the project's outputs at scientific conferences, congresses, symposia, exhibitions, trade shows, fairs	At least 6 presentations	Researchers, Academia, Public Institutions, Government Bodies, Industry

Capacity Building Workshops Two-way communication	Train value chain actors on the novel digital technology developed via SEA2SEE.	at least 100 stakeholders;	Value Chain Actors
Final conference (M48) + Workshop with brokerage events Two-way communication	Summary of work done, dissemination of results Focus on Exploitation	12 interested seafood value chain actors reached	Industry, Investors
Synergies/Networking Two-way	Knowledge transfer; Boost impact through joint communication/dissemination	4 related projects / 5 coordinators involved	Research Community ; Regulators ; Industry
Videos (M6, M42) One way communication	Spread information on social media and the web; illustrate project’s objectives, activities and impact.	2 videos – 2 -3 min; 1000 views per video	All

Table 6. SEA2SEE communication and dissemination KPIs

4.2. MONITORING DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES AND EVENT PARTICIPATION

To facilitate an accurate monitoring and assessment of the dissemination and communication activities and gain better understanding of the impact of the performed actions, the partners of SEA2SEE Consortium are asked to file a report every 6 months, using the created for this purpose Communication and Dissemination Tracker (number and type of stakeholders reached in events, articles published, flyers distributed, events attended, etc.). The information gathered via the tracker will be used during the regular reporting periods in the EC portal. It is populated with data by each WP leader and sent to WP7 leader and project coordinator. A separate reporting template is provided for scientific publications.

Summary for reporting											
SEA2SEE Dissemination and communication activities											
Type of dissemination and communication activities	Number of Events	Description	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Estimated Number of persons reached							
				Industry	Civil Society	General Public	Policy Makers	Media	Investors	Customers	Other
Organisation of a Conference											
Organisation of a Workshop											
Press release											
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)											
Exhibition											
Flyer											
Training											
Social Media											
Website											
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)											
Participation to a Conference											
Participation to a Workshop											
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop											
Video/Film											
Brokerage Event											
Pitch Event											
Trade Fair											
Participation in activities organized jointly with other EU project(s)											
Other											
Total Funding Amount Used	€	-									

Do Not report on the total dissemination Summary, use the sheet assigned to your institution

Figure 18. SEA2SEE Dissemination and Communication Tracker

Furthermore, the development of a separate event reporting template is underway for partners to provide information regarding the activities they have been involved in to represent SEA2SEE project, either as participants or organizers. In addition to reporting the type, location, dates and topic of these events, the average number of participants and the interest groups they are affiliated with are also monitored in order to keep track of the progress the communication and dissemination objectives are reached with.

Some of the overall tracked data is summarized below:

- Number of scientific papers with name and impact factor of the journal
- Number of attended conferences and exhibitions
- Number of workshops
- Number of presented presentations/posters
- Number of event attendees
- Videos produced and number of video views
- Social media posts and engagement rate on partners' pages and accounts

All partners should save evidence of the activities conducted. In the case of events, these could be photos taken from events, registration sheets and/or presentations.

The regular monitoring of the activities leads to properly assessing the effectiveness of the plan and a timely identification of potential gaps or discrepancies to readjust communication if necessary. It also brings about the possibility to see which are the actions with the largest impact on the stakeholders (both in quantitative and qualitative terms) and intensify on them.

Naturally, the communication and dissemination reporting from partners facilitates the future updates of the plan as well as the preparation of the final Report on Dissemination and Communication activities (D7.3).

4.3. WEBSITE AND SOCIAL NETWORKS MONITORING

SEA2SEE website's metrics, statistics, trends, and the impact of each activity performed on the website are analyzed by EP as WP7 lead via Google Analytics, on a regular basis. Reports on various performance indicators will be prepared to inform project partners of website's performance, such as:

- o Unique users count visiting the website
- o Average visit time and bounce rate
- o Languages and geographic locations of visitors
- o Number of page views and average page views per visit
- o Top landing page and bounce rate for different pages

Google Analytics data will be collected every 3 months and reported to the Consortium at the progress management meetings. Respective adjustments will be made to improve users' experience if required.

The Insights tools of social media accounts will be utilized to collect analytical information on the profile of SEA2SEE followers as well as the engagement rate in terms of reactions, comments, shares, recommendations. This information would equip partners with better understand what content works best in terms of SEA2SEE messaging that resonates accordingly with the target personas as well as other factors like most appropriate timing of post, frequency, communication style and type of content. The monitoring of these parameters provides valuable information as to which type of social media appears to be most efficient in reaching our target groups and could subsequently justify closing some of the accounts if they prove to be failing the initial performance expectations.

4.2. MANAGEMENT

4.2.1. ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

WP7 leader (EP) takes responsibility for the steering and implementation of WP7 tasks along with the task leaders for Task 7.3 and Task 7.4, Ethic Ocean and Vitagora, respectively who have jointly contributed to the preparation of the Dissemination and Communication Plan. It is EP's continuing responsibility to keep track of it throughout the project and provide necessary updates, following all partners inputs during the regular 6-month project meetings. Partners active involvement in the communication and dissemination of the project is critical for achieving its general and communicative objectives as well as CD plan's alignment with the exploitation goals.

As partners in an EU-funded project, Consortium members commit to regularly creating content for SEA2SEE's social media, website and newsletter, to engage stakeholders and inform them proactively about the progress of their work activities, and later on - the achieved results. They are reminded to tag

SEA2SEE in their social media posts, stories, reels, videos and use the relevant hashtags, so that maximum project’s visibility is achieved.

In an effort to facilitate content contribution, in addition to the reminder content and event collection email that is sent to partners monthly, a calendar planner is created, as a visual aid. Each partner is responsible for providing a blog-post-like article for the website, social media or newsletter, with relevant images, for their assigned weeks in the calendar. Furthermore, partners are encouraged to produce own informational materials meeting their respective communication needs while complying with the visual identity of the project, outlined in detail in the graphic charter.

Figure 19. SEA2SEE Content Planner

4.2.2. COMMUNICATION WAVES AND DELIVERABLES

WP7 is a horizontal work package which runs during the lifespan of the 48-month project. As mentioned earlier, the communication and dissemination endeavor unfolds in three phases correlated with the progress of the project and each with its strategic focus and objectives. An illustrative summary is proposed below while a more detailed elaboration is found in Section III. Implementation.

Figure 20. SEA2SEE Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Waves

Deliverables of high quality are essential to the success and continuing impact of the project. All WP7 deliverables are available to the public and are accessible long after the project's completion. The table below lists the deliverables in WP7 with their number, title, description, lead beneficiary, type, dissemination level and due date.

Deliverables and Milestones							
WP No	Del /MS No	Title	Lead Beneficiary	Description	Due Date	Type	Dissemination Level
WP7	D7.1	Website and social media	EP	Report on SEA2SEE website and social media	31 Dec 2022	R	PU
WP7	D7.2	Communication and Dissemination Plan	EP	Plan for defining key messages, positioning statements and target audiences and selecting the appropriate tools and channels to meet their information needs.	31 Dec 2022	R	PU
WP7	D7.3	Report on the Dissemination and Communication activities	EP	Report on the dissemination and communication campaigns performed to promote the project and disseminate its results to key stakeholders and the general public	30 Jun 2026	R	PU

WP7	D7.4	Synergy plan	VITAG ORA	A Synergy plan will be elaborated to ensure cooperation with stakeholders, European Commission services and initiatives and with other relevant projects to leverage potential synergies at EU and national level	31 Dec 2022	R	PU
WP7	MS9	Dissemination and Communication Plan	EP	D7.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan available	31 Dec 2022	N/A	N/A
WP7	MS10	Synergy plan	VITAG ORA	D7.4 Synergy Plan available	31 Dec 2022	N/A	N/A

Table 7. List of SEA2SEE Deliverables and Milestones

INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

All Consortium partners are contributors to the dissemination and communication activities under WP7 and as such they use their own networks as detailed above, for the following purposes:

- Identifying and informing about dissemination opportunities (e.g., events, publications, etc.),
- Providing relevant information and documentation to enrich the project website,
- Posting news and project results in own digital channels – website, social media, newsletter

The dissemination of the project’s results should not be expected to cause intellectual property rights or copyright issues to SEA2SEE partners. To ensure this, all partners are duly aware about the content of each dissemination product related to their activities by following the publication approval process, as described in the CA. In the unlikely case of copyrights infringement, partners can refuse the dissemination of their own outputs.

5. EC COMMUNICATION REQUIREMENTS

As a beneficiary of the EU Horizon Europe programme, project partners hold the legal obligation to acknowledge the received EU funding and display the EU emblem in all communication materials.

HOW TO DISPLAY THE ACKNOWLEDGEMENT OF EU FUNDING

DISPLAY THE EU EMBLEM

The European Union emblem and the funding statement must be displayed prominently on all printed and digital products, websites, social media channels and other communication products.

Co-funded by
the European Union

USE A DISCLAIMER

Use the following disclaimers whenever using the funding logo:

“Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research and Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Although not required, the Grant Agreement number could also be added:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No. 101060564 (SEA2SEE).”

Horizon Europe social media related guidance on the EU acknowledgment will be available soon.

The information contained herein is also available in the project’s Graphic Charter.

6. CONCLUSION

The Communication and Dissemination Plan of SEA2SEE lays strong foundation for building general awareness about the project and its mission, and triggering interest in its first outcomes that is gradually growing into a continuing engagement with the achieved progress and developments. It is conceived with the intent to be upgraded during the next, result yielding phases of the project, while reinforcing dissemination activities to highlight the outputs and possibilities for their exploitation. The key messages are conveyed through actively utilizing digital and offline communication channels, networking opportunities and demonstration and validation of the results at specifically designated fishery and aquaculture pilot sites. The planned events provide for the occurrence of both unilateral and bilateral communication with the identified target groups, with the latter being more user engaging and happening predominantly in social media and during the workshops. The CD plan aims to shape SEA2SEE's reputation for a project developing innovative technological solution for increasing sustainable seafood traceability, transparency and consumers' preference towards sustainable seafood choices. The devised communication and dissemination strategies are closely intertwined with the engagement actions planned under WP1 and WP2. However, the successful execution of the plan utterly depends on the collective participation and contribution of all partners.

It is important to highlight that this Plan is not complete without the Synergy Plan (D7.4) and Project Website and Social Media report (D7.1) since the outlined activities in all of these documents are interrelated and therefore, mutually influencing the final outcomes, impact and ultimately, positive accomplishment.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

Deliverable 7.2 is developed in accordance with the provisions outlined in the following related documents:

- SEA2SEE Grant Agreement,
- SEA2SEE Consortium Agreement Nr. 101060564

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	SEA2SEE Grant Agreement	SEA2SEE Partners' Space
2	SEA2SEE Consortium Agreement Nr. 101060564	SEA2SEE Partners' Space